

SynAir-G

Functional wireless communications

Deliverable number	D5.5
Due date	31.08.2023
Nature	Deliverable
Dissemination level	PU-Public
Work Package	5
Lead Beneficiary	UoP
Contributing Beneficiaries	

Project & Document Information

Grant Agreement No	101057271	Acronym	SynAir-G
Project Full Title	Disrupting Noxious Synergies of Indoor Air Pollutants and their Impact in Childhood Health and Wellbeing using Advanced Intelligent Multi-sensing and Green Interventions		
Call	HORIZON-HLTH-2021-ENVHLTH-02		
Topic	HORIZON-HLTH-2021-ENVHLTH-02-02	Type of action	RIA
Coordinator	National and Kapodistrian University of Athens		
Start Date	01/09/2022	Duration	48 months
Deliverable	D5.5	Work Package	WP 5
Document Type	DEM	Dissemination Level	PU
Lead beneficiary	PANEPISTIMIO PATRON (UoP)		
Responsible author	Sotiris Nikolettseas (UoP)		
Contractual due date	[31/08/2023]	Actual submission date	[01/09/2023]

Authoring, Revision & QA Information

Deliverable Contributors	
Contributor Name	Organisation (Acronym)
Sotiris Nikolettseas	Panepistimio Patron (UoP)
Gabriel Filios	Panepistimio Patron (UoP)
Kyriakos Giannopoulos	Panepistimio Patron (UoP)

Version History				
Version	Date	%	Changes	Author
0.1	01.08.2023	50%	First consolidated version ready	Kyriakos Giannopoulos
0.2	20.08.2023	90%	Consolidated version ready	Gabriel Filios
1.0	31.08.2023	100%	Final version ready for review	Sotiris Nikolettseas

Quality Control (includes peer & quality reviewing)			
Date	Version	Name (Organisation)	Role & Scope
31.08.2023	1.0	Nikos Papadopoulos (NKUA)	Project Coordinator

Table of Contents

1. Introduction.....	5
1.1. Purpose of the document.....	5
1.2. Structure of the document.....	5
2. Communication requirements	6
3. Communication solution selection.....	9
4. Configuration.....	11
5. Installation of router in the Sensor Box.....	17
6. Insertion and setup of SIM card by the user	21

1. Introduction

1.1. Purpose of the document

This document presents the wireless communication solution that provides connectivity to internet for all the sensing and mitigation devices (of WP1 and WP5) that will be installed into the classrooms.

Following the requirements that came out from the specification assessment of all devices (T5.5.1), the designed the communication solution that covers all the needs, then the communication devices configured accordingly (T5.5.2) and tested (T5.5.3).

1.2. Structure of the document

The document is organized into the following sections:

- Section 2 – Communication requirements: presents an overview of the technical specifications for all the sensing and mitigation devices and the requirements for the communication.
- Section 3 – Communication solution selection: provides the main features of the communication solution we select to use.
- Section 4 – Configuration: describes in detail how RUT200 was configured at the development phase.
- Section 5 – Installation of router in the Sensor Box: In this section we show how to power up RUT200, explain the various Led indications and how it will be installed in the Sensor Box.
- Section 6 – Insertion and setup of SIM card by the user: explains how the user can insert the SIM card and set up the mobile internet connection.

2. Communication requirements

To design the appropriate solution for the communication that provides connectivity to internet for the SynAir-G experimentation devices, we collected the technical specifications for all the sensing and mitigation devices that will be installed into the classrooms. In the following table are summarized the specifications from the responsible partners that provide each sensor of mitigation device.

	Device info	Responsible Partner	Supported communication technologies	Details
1	ENSENSIA chemical pollutants sensing device	FORTH	WiFi, 4G, LoRaWAN	The sensors measure every 20 sec, we collect the data every 2 min and then we average them. The average values are sent to the server where they are stored. Thus, every 2 min we have to collect measurements. Per day the size of collected data is approximately 500 KBytes
2	APS-400 Pollensense	AUTH	WiFi, Ethernet, Cellular	<p>The device samples 24/7 365 as long as the device is hooked up to a power supply and internet source. We have imaging coming in approximately every 30-90 seconds and the data is rolled up to the Pollen Sense Portal on an hourly basis.</p> <p>We are continually collecting air samples and tracking how long each frame is exposed to the incoming air. New samples are collected while other samples are imaged. Imaging happens on roughly at a 2 minute interval. This data is then taken and calculated into intervals of hourly, daily, weekly, monthly, and yearly. The size of data is estimated roughly between 25 and 30 GB per month per sensor.</p> <p>Data Access by App, Web Portal and API</p>
3	Biosensors	CNR	WiFi	A new sensor will be designed from CNR and in collaboration with CYRIC it will be integrated on a microcontroller with WiFi connectivity. This Task is in progress and the device will be ready in the next year.

4	Canarin Nano	CHUM	V1: GSM (2G) V2: GSM and GPS	The U-BLOX SARA-U270 GSM module provides cellular connectivity and allows the device to transmit data to a remote server.
5	ALANA biological air purifying mitigation device	TEQOYA	WiFi	<p>It supports two different communication approaches:</p> <p><u>Communication 1:</u></p> <p>The devices being on the same WLAN network (devices in the same group) share their actual fan speed (when a user change the speed of one device, the other devices align on the same speed). The pairing of devices form a group can be easily configured with a smartphone. There is one "master" per group and its definition is dynamic (if the master is switched off, the group organizes to define a new one). It is recommended to installed 3 to 4 Alana per classroom.</p> <p>Frequency = 30s (configurable)</p> <p>Size of data on Wi-Fi = approx. 20 bytes for Master messages and 10 bytes for other devices messages</p> <p><u>Communication 2:</u></p> <p>The "group master" (not the other devices in the same group) sends its status (typically its fan speed) to a server and asks for status change order (this enables the server to change the purification power depending on the measured pollution, or to save power during configurable days and/or time of day).</p> <p>Note that we assume that all devices in one group are on the same position and will execute the master order, so the whole group is seen as one single device by the server.</p> <p>Frequency = 15s (configurable)</p> <p>JSON format (when communicating with our server it calls a HTTP REST API)</p> <p>Size of data :</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - raw data = approx. 120 bytes

				- encapsulated in http messages = approx. 600 bytes up (device to server), 500 bytes down
6	Air filtering mitigation device	NAAVA	4G	It stores the data at about 5 min interval for multiple years so the data can be pulled via CSV file for a needed time frame. Also graphs are available in Naava.app in real time for the devices. Data is also available via REST API if required. NAAVA also tracks a few other parameters but they're not relevant for the study of this project (water level and usage, fan RPMs etc.).

Transmitting data requirements

Given the specifications of the sensor devices provided by the responsible partners, we have the following estimations of the data usage of each sensor:

	Partner	Device info	Connection via WiFi or 3G/4G	Data per month
1	FORTH	ENSENSIA chemical pollutants sensing device	Both	15 MB
2	AUTH	APS-400 Pollensense	Both	25 - 30 GB
3	CNR	Biosensors	WiFi	
4	CHUM	Canarin Nano	GSM (2G)	
5	TEQOYA	ALANA biological air purifying mitigation device	WiFi	5 – 100 MB
6	NAAVA	Air filtering mitigation device	4G	

3. Communication solution selection

Based on the various requirements of the project and the sensors designed to be installed into the Sensor Boxes, we settled to install in each sensor box a router that supports 4G connectivity and provides Wi-Fi connectivity to the sensing and mitigation devices if each classroom.

After the research we made for the available solutions, we ended up to use the RUT200 4G routers from the manufacturer Teltonica. Below we present and analyze the main features of the RUT200 that cover the need of our implementation.

- **WiFi:** The RUT200 can be a WiFi Access Point that covers the main requirement for the devices that need WiFi connection for Internet access. Also, the RUT200 can be configured through a UI using a web browser from a PC that is connected via WiFi to the router. It is not necessary for the router to be connected to the Internet to log into the UI. More information is provided in the next chapters.
- **Autonomy:** The RUT200 provides an Internet connection via 4G, as long as a SIM card providing 4G connection is inserted. This is important as it is not available LAN or WAN network in classrooms.
- **Flexibility:** The RUT200 also supports Internet connection using Ethernet if it is available. Specifically:
 - The router contains a LAN port. Using this port, we can connect one device to the RUT200 and, if the RUT200 provides Internet connectivity, then the second device is connected to the Internet. We can also connect to the UI to configure the RUT200 using the LAN port. Specifically, we connect a computer to the RUT200 via an Ethernet cable and from a browser we enter the address IP `http://192.168.1.1`. More information in the corresponding chapter below.
 - The router contains a WAN port. Using this port we can connect the RUT200 to a LAN port of another router or modem that provides an Internet connection. In this way the RUT200 can provide Internet connection to other devices connected to it, without the need of a SIM card.
- **Industrial Type:** It has a metal chassis with several add-ons for mounting, and it is small compared to commercial routers used in homes and is compact.
- **External antennas:** External antennas (2 for Mobile, 1 for WiFi) are supplied with the product which must be installed on the RUT200 for its various functions. They can be easily mounted and provide flexibility in their orientation, which will be very important for the placement of the router into the box it will be mounted on.
- **Power supply:** the RUT200 can operate with various power supply values, specifically in a range with values from 9 to 30 VDC and thus is adaptable to the various standards of each country. In addition, power can be supplied using 4-PINs and can also be connected using simple cables, without the need of the transformer supplied with the product.
- **Remote Control:** Teltonica provides a service through which we can configure and monitor the RUT200 remotely. Specifically, the RUT200 must be registered using the Serial Number of the product in this service and then we can log in to the UI of the respective router, either to configure or monitor the operation of the router. However, in order to have this possibility

we need to register to the Teltonika service which requires a monthly subscription and make some settings on the RUT200, specifically in the RMS section of the Setup Wizard.

SynAir-G is funded by the European Union under Grant Agreement No 101057271. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HADEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

4. Configuration

A principle that was followed during the configuration of RUT200 is that the routed need only to be mounted, connected to the power supply and then start operating in a plug-and-play manner. In order for this to be achieved, we needed to make some configuration before delivering the product. In the following steps we describe in detail how RUT200 was configured at the development phase.

Step 1: Connecting a computer to the RUT200

There are two ways:

- *Connecting via WiFi:* We find the RUT200 SSID in the available networks and enter the necessary password to connect (one can find this at the back of the chassis).
- *Connect via Ethernet:* We use an Ethernet cable and connect one end to the corresponding port of the computer (if available) and the other end to the LAN port on the RUT200.

Step 2: Connecting to the UI of RUT200

In a browser of your choice (Google Chrome, Mozilla Firefox, Internet Explorer, etc.) type in the address <http://192.168.1.1> and press Enter. This step will direct you to the UI's login form.

Step 3: Login to the UI

Type in the "Username" and "Password" fields the Username and Password which are located on the back of the RUT200 chassis (the last two credentials) and press Enter.

It will then direct us to the UI, where we have to fill in a new administrator password to proceed to the UI.

Step 4: Setting up the RUT200

In the left part of the UI there is header. Go to *System > Setup Wizard*, where there are 5 tabs with router's configuration. In the next steps we show the changes that need to be made.

Step 4.1: General

In this step, an initial configuration must be done in order to have the full capabilities of configuration as administrator. Firstly, we change the configuration mode from *Basic* to *Advanced* and synchronize the local time of the router to the current country's system time. To do this, just press the *SYNC WITH BROWSER* button. After this, press *NEXT* to apply the configuration.

Step 4.2: LAN

In this tab the LAN mode configuration is shown. We made no changes in this section, so we just press **NEXT**.

Step 4.3: Mobile

In this tab we can make a basic configuration for the connection of the router to the Internet, provided that the router will work using a SIM card. If the SIM card has a PIN, then this PIN has to be inserted in the corresponding field, else if the SIM card has no PIN, we leave it empty. We chose to leave this field empty for the moment. Additionally, we chose that AutoAPN is enabled, as most of the Internet providers have their APN already stored in the SIM card.

Step 4.4: Wireless

In this tab we have to configure the WiFi settings, which are the Network name, a.k.a. ESSID, and the WiFi password. These credentials are specified by the associated company and we will change them for security reasons.

Step 4.5: RMS

As described in a previous section, RUT200 has a feature where we can monitor, configure and provide support remotely. In this tab the associated settings are located, which are the Connection type, the Hostname of the service of Teltonika which enables this feature and the Port of this service. These are pre-defined and should not be changed if one needs to have remote access to the router via Teltonika's associated service. However, one can maintain a custom server for this purpose and so these fields need to be changed accordingly. We chose to not make any change in these settings for the moment. Additionally, the STATUS table shows the connection status of RUT200 to this service. If the device is not registered in Teltonika's service, then no connection will be made and will show a connection Failure.

List of configuration settings

Overall, the settings that had to be made on these tabs are summarized in the table below. Those values that were not changed when the Router was configured have value "Yes" in the "Pre-configured" column, while those that were changed have a value of "No".

Tab	Table	Attribute	Value	Pre-configured
General	WEBUI SETTINGS	Language	English	Yes
		Configuration Mode	Advanced	No
	GENERAL SETTINGS	Current System Time	SYNC WITH BROWSER	No
LAN	LAN CONFIGURATION	IPv4 address	192.168.1.1	Yes
		IPv4 netmask	255.255.255.0	Yes
	DHCP CONFIGURATION	Enable DHCP	Enable	Yes
		Start IP	192.168.1.100	Yes
		End IP	192.168.1.249	Yes
Lease time	12/Hours	Yes		
Mobile	MOBILE CONFIGURATION: MOB1S1A1	Auto APN	On	Yes
		PIN	Empty (Depends on the settings of each SIM card)	No
Wireless	WIFI 2.4GHZ	Enable	On	Yes

		ESSID	SynAirGbox01 ... SynAirGbox25 (Depends on the box that the router will be installed)	No
		Password	This value was changed, but we hide it from this deliverable for security reasons	No
RMS	RMS SETTINGS	Connection type	Enabled	Yes
		Hostname	rms.teltonika-networks.com	Yes
		Port	15009	Yes

5. Installation of router in the Sensor Box

In this section we show how to power up RUT200, explain the various indications and how to be installed in the Sensor Box.

Powering up RUT200

The router has 4-PIN power socket and can be powered by a 9-30 VDC power supply. Below a picture and each PIN meaning is shown (**MIND THE ORIENTATION OF THE PLUG**).

Power Socket Pinout

No.	Description	Wire color
1	Power	Red
2	Ground	Black
3	Input	Green
4	Output	White

Insert the power supply adapter provided with the product to the socket then insert it to the plug. Alternatively, one can make a custom connection to the 4 pins, provided that the Voltage remains in the specified VDC range.

LED Indications

Below are shown the various LEDs of RUT200 along with the descriptions.

Power LED: The power LED is located on the bottom left corner of the front panel, just under the power connector.

It can perform two different actions, as shown below:

ACTION	DESCRIPTION
LED turned ON	Router is powered up
LED turned OFF	Router is not powered up

Ethernet port LEDs: The Ethernet port LEDs are located on the router's front panel, under each respective Ethernet port.

They represent activity happening on the router's Ethernet ports, as show below:

ACTION	DESCRIPTION
LED turned ON	Operating as a 10/100 Mbps connection
LED turned OFF	No link established
LED blinking	Connection established and there is activity on this port (data being transferred)
LEDs light up and turn OFF in sequence from WAN port to LAN1 port	The router is in the bootloader menu state*

Connection status LEDs: The connection status LEDs are located on the left side of the front panel, between the power connector and the signal strength indication LEDs:

The LED displays the router's current connection state and network type among a few other things, as shown below:

ACTION	DESCRIPTION
2G, 3G and 4G LEDs blinking every 1 second	No SIM or bad PIN
Blinking from 2G LED to 4G LED repeatedly	Attempting to connect to a mobile network operator
2G/3G/4G LED blinking every 1 sec	Connected to 2G/3G/4G, no data session established
2G/3G/4G LED turned on	Connected to 2G/3G/4G with data session
2G/3G/4G LED blinking rapidly	Connected to 2G/3G/4G with data session and data is being transferred

Signal strength LEDs: The signal strength LEDs are located in the center of the front panel, to the right of the connection status LEDs:

Each lit up LED represents a different value of the router’s current signal strength in RSSI, as shown below:

NO. OF LIT UP LEDs	SIGNAL STRENGTH VALUE
0	≤ -111 dBm
1	-110 dBm to -97 dBm
2	-96 dBm to -82 dBm
3	-81 dBm to -67 dBm
4	-66 dBm to -52 dBm
5	≥ -51 dBm

After the router gets powered up, the LEDs will turn ON for about 5 seconds, then all strength signals will be blinking for about 40 seconds or until the router’s modem registers on a network. After this, the LEDs will start displaying the router’s current signal strength and the type of connection to the Internet (i.e. 4G).

Installing RUT200 in the Sensor Box.

The development of the individual components and the integration of the Sensor Box is in progress as the corresponding Task 5.2 - SynAir-G integrated autonomous sensing platform ends at month M39. In the next pictures we can see the position of the router into the Sensor Box and how the users can have access to insert the Sim Card.

More details will be provided to the Deliverable D5.2 (SynAir-G integrated multi-sensor prototype) when the integration will be completed.

6. Insertion and setup of SIM card by the user

SIM card insertion

In order to insert or to exert the SIM card in the RUT200 follow Steps 1 to 4 as shown below:

SIM card insertion

- 1 Push the SIM holder button with the SIM needle.
- 2 Pull out the SIM holder.
- 3 Insert your SIM card into the SIM holder.
- 4 Slide the SIM holder back into the router.

While inserting the SIM card and the SIM holder keep the orientation as shown in the picture so that no damage is done by mistake. Also make sure that the whole SIM card is placed in the SIM card holder.

Note that the SIM holder is compatible with 4FF SIM cards. If smaller SIM card is to be inserted, 2FF for example, an adapter for 2FF to 4FF SIM card has to be used. No such adapter is provided along with the product.

Below are shown the different standards for the SIM cards and the various adapters.

All SIM card types by size

Adapter types

3FF to 2FF adapter

4FF to 2FF adapter

Below are given the exact specifications of the SIM cards and SIM adapters:

SIM Card Format	Length (Mm)	Width (Mm)	Thickness (Mm)
Mini-SIM (2FF)	25.00	15.00	0.76
Micro-SIM (3FF)	15.00	12.00	0.76
Nano-SIM (4FF)	12.30	8.80	0.67

Setting up RUT200 with a SIM card

To make it easier for end users to install SIM card, we have set up RUT200 to work automatically when the user inserts the card with no need to change any settings on it.

For this reason, RUT200 was set up to work with a SIM card that has no PIN. If the SIM card has a PIN, the easier way for the user is to contact the appropriate Internet provider of the SIM card and ask them to remove the PIN of the SIM card. RUT200 should then work fine when the SIM card is inserted in a plug-n-play way.

If the PIN of the SIM card cannot be removed, then the user has to log into the UI of RUT200 and go to Network > Mobile > General setting and insert into the PIN field type in the PIN of the SIM card. Then click Save and Apply at the bottom-right of this page. After a while RUT200 shall connect to the internet and operate fine.

Then, one of the next actions might have to be done, in case the Internet provider of the SIM card needs to setup the APN.

1) Automatic connection: To ensure that automatic connection is enabled, go to Network > Interfaces > General the press the edit button of mob1s1a1 cell.

A new window will pop up. Go to GENERAL SETTINGS section of this pop up and make sure that AutoAPN is enabled.

2) Manual connection: If the APN of the provider has to be inserted manually, firstly turn off the AutoAPN of the GENERAL SETTINGS section (as shown in the previous step).

Some new options will appear. Then choose APN field to be Custom and at the Custom APN field type in the APN of the Internet provider.

